

Removal of Humic Acid by UiO-66(Zr) and MIL-100(Fe) Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) Adsorption

Wrya Omer Mala Abdalla

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;
UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China

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Abstract:

The escalating presence of humic acid (HA) in aquatic systems poses significant ecological and potable water treatment challenges, altering the color, taste, and odor of water and fueling algal blooms that deplete oxygen levels to the detriment of aquatic life. Traditional techniques like coagulation-flocculation, membrane filtration, oxidation fall short in efficiency due to its small fraction of HA. This study confronts the pervasive issue of HA contamination by leveraging the advanced properties of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs). In this work, two representative MOFs are synthesized and

well characterized. Then, their capability for removal HA by adsorption process in water for HA treatment are detailed evaluated. The findings from this research extend beyond academic curiosity, offering actionable insights for water treatment facilities and environmental management agencies. The synthesis of MOFs which are UiO-66(Zr), MIL-100(Fe). Each MOFs have been applied to remove HA by adsorption under different condition. The effect of contacting time, initial pH, adsorbent dosage has been evaluated. After adsorption experiment, MOF samples prepared to dry and went through characterization. Removal of HA by MOF adsorption showed UiO-66(Zr) and MIL-100(Fe) examined rapid reaching equilibrium state with 10-15 min. Among various pH conditions, UiO-66(Zr) and MIL-100(Fe) showed the highest adsorption capacity under acidic conditions. MIL-100(Fe) achieves a higher maximum adsorption capacity than MIL-100(Fe). MOF after adsorption samples went through characterizations and their remained characteristics indicating the adsorption not affected the structure of the MOFs.

Keywords: *Humic acid, UiO-66(Zr), MIL-100(Fe), MOFs Adsorption.*

Introduction

The amount of natural organic matter (NOM) in water bodies has lately been discovered to grow as well as vary greatly (Eikebrokk, Vogt, & Liltved, 2004). It is feasible to divide the components of NOM into two fundamental categories: non-humic substances, which include things like amino acids, polysaccharides,

hydrocarbons, carbohydrates, lipids, waxes, resins, and low molecular organic acids, and complex heterogeneous humic substances (Eikebrokk et al., 2004). These elements contribute to micropollutant transmission and produce water color. The taste and fragrance of the water are also negatively impacted by their presence. According to estimates, humic compounds make up half of

the total organic carbon in water (Sillanpää, 2014; Sillanpää, Ncibi, Matilainen, & Vepsäläinen, 2018). Dissolved Organic Matter (DOM) is a subset of Natural Organic Matter (NOM), which includes all organic materials found in natural water systems. DOM specifically refers to those parts of NOM that are small enough to remain in solution when the water is filtered through a filter capable of trapping particles larger than a few tenths of a micron. Humic Acid (HA) is a significant component of DOM, comprising a variety of complex molecules formed through the biological and chemical breakdown of plant and animal material. These molecules are characterized by their ability to form soluble complexes with ions and their yellow to dark brown color, which can significantly influence the chemical and biological properties of water. Humic acid can alter water's chemical and physical characteristics. Humic acid changes the color and odor of water, affect the quantities of dissolved O, N, P, and S, and act as a transporter for harmful contaminants such as pesticides and radionuclides (Knauer, Homazava, Junghans, & Werner, 2017; Santschi et al., 2017).

Furthermore, effectiveness of PAC Pre-dosing in Different Waters: The study suggests that while PAC pre-dosing 2 hours before coagulation (PAC2h-AS) has certain advantages in HA water treatment, such as forming stronger and more compact flocs, the same benefits are not observed in HA-kaolin water treatment. This indicates a potential research gap in understanding the varying effectiveness of PAC pre-dosing in different types of water matrices, particularly those with varying levels of inorganic particles (Bonvin, Jost, Randin, Bonvin, & Kohn, 2016).

Therefore, further research is needed to validate the effectiveness of the adsorption on MOFs at a larger scale. In this study, we examined two different types of MOFs which are they Zirconium 1,4-dicarboxybenzene (UiO-66(Zr)), Matériaux de l'Institut Lavoisier (MIL) with "Fe" denoting the incorporation of iron in its structure (MIL-100(Fe)), and we found out which one is best material to adsorb and best removal efficiency.

Materials and Methods

Table 1. Chemicals Used in this Experiment

Reagent	Molecular Formula	Grade	Reagent Manufacturer
Humic acid	C ₉ H ₉ NO ₆	AR	Shanghai Aladdin Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd
Sodium Hydroxide	NaOH	AR	Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd.
Hydrochloric Acid	(HCl)	AR	Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd.
N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF)	HCON(CH ₃) ₂	AR	Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd.
Zirconium dichloride oxide octahydrate	Cl ₂ H ₁₈ O ₉ Zr	AR	J&K Scientific Ltd
Terephthalic acid	C ₈ H ₆ O ₄	AR	TCI
Formic acid	HCOOH	AR	Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd.
Methanol anhydrous	CH ₃ OH	AR	Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd.
Ethanol absolute	C ₂ H ₆ O	AR	Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd.
Iron (III) chloride hexahydrate for synthesis	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	AR	J&K Scientific Ltd
1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylic acid trimesic acid (H ₃ BTC)	C ₉ H ₆ O ₆	AR	TCI

Characterization

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction XRD patterns were recorded using a diffractometer (MiniFlex600-C, Rigaku Corporation, Japan) with a Cu target K α

radiation $\lambda = 1.54056$ while operating at 40 kV and 40 mA. The XRD scans were performed in the range of 5° to 50° with a step size of 0.01° and a scan rate of 10°/min. XRD analysis provides information about the crystalline structure and phase composition of the material.

providing information about unit cell parameters, crystal symmetry, and atomic positions.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Surface morphologies, shape, size and elemental compositions of pristine, after adsorption and after enhanced coagulation were examined for UiO-66(Zr), MIL-100(Fe), ZIF-8 and Al-fum using SEM (FEI Verios 460L, Thermo Fisher Scientific, China Co., Ltd.). In SEM characterization, MOF samples coated with gold before analysis to enhance conductivity, which reduces charging effects during imaging. This coating also improves resolution and contrast, protects delicate samples from electron beam damage, and prevents contamination, ensuring more accurate and reliable analysis overall.

N₂ Sorption

The surface area of the synthesized MOFs (UiO-66, MIL-100 Fe, ZIF-8, Al-fum) samples were determined using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method based on adsorption data. BET analysis provides information about the specific surface area and pore structure of the material. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms were acquired at 77 K using a BET analyzer (ASAP 2020M, Micromeritics (Shanghai) Instrument Co., Ltd.).

Prior to the N₂ uptake experiments, degassing was performed at 120 °C under vacuum conditions for 48 hours to eliminate any foreign gases or vapors adsorbed on the surface of the MOF samples, which could interfere with the precision of the measurements. The Auto-Sorb apparatus measured the adsorbed or desorbed volumes of nitrogen at relative pressures ranging from 0.001 to slightly under 1.0. By analyzing the N₂-assisted adsorption-desorption data, the specific surface area, pore volume. Typically, the isotherm data at saturated conditions evaluate the total pore volume of the materials. The existence of macro pores can be detected when a significant increase is observed at saturated pressure.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR)

spectroscopy was conducted using (Nicolet 5700, Thermo Fisher Scientific China Co., Ltd.) in the range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹. This analysis aimed to determine characterize the different functional groups of the MOFs.

Adsorption

Calibration Curve

A stock solution of humic acid was prepared by dissolving 1 g of humic acid in 62.5 mL of 0.1 M NaOH solution (added to ensure complete dissolution of HA), followed by dilution with distilled water to obtain a final volume of 1 L. This stock solution was further diluted for use in the experiments. During the experiments 3L of HA stock solution been used.

The calibration curve for Humic Acid (HA) concentration was established through a meticulous process as shown from Figure 3.1, beginning with the preparation of seven 250 mL flasks, each containing different concentrations of HA (1, 3, 5, 10, 30, 50, 100 mg/L) mixed with 80 mL of purified water. preparation of HA experiment conducted in a thermostatic shaker operating at 400 rpm. This setup ensured a range of HA concentrations to accurately define the relationship between concentration and absorbance. The entire procedure was conducted at a controlled temperature of 305°K to maintain consistency and prevent temperature-induced variability in the readings.

The collected absorbance data at 321 nm for each known HA concentration served as the foundation for plotting the calibration curve. By graphing the absorbance (A.u.) against HA concentration (mg/L), a linear relationship was established, indicated by the linear regression equation and the statistical parameters derived from it. This calibration curve is a critical tool for determining unknown HA concentrations in samples by comparing their absorbance values at 321 nm against the curve, leveraging the direct proportionality between HA concentration and its absorbance as dictated by the Beer-Lambert Law.

Adsorption Experiments

Kinetic adsorption experiments were conducted in a thermostatic shaker operating at 400 rpm.

Erlenmeyer flasks of 250 mL containing 80 mL of HA solution and 40 mg of the respective MOFs were used for each experiment. The initial pH of the HA solution was adjusted using 0.1 M HCl or NaOH solution. pH measurements were recorded using an HI 8424 pH meter. To evaluate the kinetics and equilibrium time for HA adsorption, contact time was varied at 0min, 3min, 5min, 10min, 20min, 30min, 1h, 1.5h, 2h, 4h, 8h while keeping the HA concentration at 50 ppm, temperature at 305 K, and pH at 6 (Naseem et al., 2022).

The effect of pH on the adsorption of HA was investigated by varying the initial pH of the solution from 4 to 8 while maintaining a constant temperature of 305 K, contact time as equilibrium time for each MOF as follows: 240 min for Al-fum, 120 min for MIL-100(Fe), 120 min for ZIF-8, and 60 min for UiO-66(Zr), and HA concentration of 50 ppm. In aiming of finding best pH removal for each MOFs.

Isotherm adsorption experiments were conducted by varying the HA concentration from 1ppm, 5ppm, 10ppm, 20ppm, 30ppm, 50ppm, 100ppm, 150ppm, 180ppm, 200ppm, 300 ppm at constant temperature (305 K), pH 6, and equilibrium contact time for each MOF: 240 min for Al-fum, 120 min for MIL-100(Fe), 120 min for ZIF-8, and 60 min for UiO-66(Zr).

To prepare the dry MOF samples, unfiltered water samples from each MOF adsorption experiment were collected and subjected to centrifugation. After centrifugation, the samples were dried using a vacuum cleaner at 80°C for a duration of 6 hours. Following drying, the samples were used for XRD, FTIR, and SEM characterization.

After each adsorption experiment, the solution was filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 41. The initial and residual HA concentrations were analyzed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU CORPORATION, UV-2600, JAPAN) at a wavelength of $\lambda_{max} = 321$ nm. The absorbance was then compared with a calibration curve to determine the respective HA concentrations in the solution and the volume solution for each MOFs with different parameter been through centrifugation, then

dried at 80C degree for 24 hours, as dry MOF samples for characterization of XRD, SEM, and FTIR.

Evaluation of Uptake Capacity (q): The uptake capacity ('q') represents the amount of humic acid (HA) adsorbed per unit mass of Co-MOF (mg/g). It was evaluated using the following Equation 1:

$$q = \frac{(C_0 - C_f)V}{m} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- C_0 (mg/g) is the initial concentration of HA.
- C_f (mg/g) is the final concentration of HA.
- V (L) is the volume of the humic acid solution.
- m (g) is the adsorbent dosage of Co-MOF.

For fitting of experimental adsorption data, experimental adsorption data was fitted with different kinetics and isotherm models. These models provide mathematical descriptions of the adsorption behavior and help in understanding the underlying mechanisms.

Adsorption Mechanisms: Understanding the adsorption mechanism is crucial for optimizing the adsorption process and predicting its efficiency. By fitting experimental data with different kinetics and isotherm models, insights into the adsorption mechanisms can be obtained.

Kinetics and Isotherm Models: Various kinetics and isotherm models can be used to describe the adsorption process. The representative

equations of different models are provided in Table 1, where kinetics models describe the rate of adsorption over time, and isotherm models describe the equilibrium relationship between the adsorbate and adsorbent at constant temperature. The kinetic adsorption data was fitted with the following classical kinetic models

Pseudo-first-order kinetic model Equation 2:

$$\ln(Q_e - Q_t) = \ln Q_e - k_1 t \quad (2)$$

Pseudo-second-order kinetic model 3:

$$\frac{t}{Q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 Q_e^2} + \frac{t}{Q_e} \quad (3)$$

where Q_e (mg g^{-1}) is the equilibrium adsorption

Figure 2. Calibration Curve for Determination of Humic Acid

Capacity of the MOFs, Q_t (mg g^{-1}) is the adsorption capacity at time t (min), k_1 (min^{-1}), k_2 ($\text{g min}^{-1} \text{mg}^{-1}$), and k_{id} ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{min}^{-0.5}$) are rate constants of pseudo-first order models, pseudo-

second-order. The isotherm adsorption data was fitted with the following adsorption isothermal models:

Langmuir isotherm model Equation 4:

$$\frac{C_e}{Q_e} = \frac{1}{b Q_{m,1}} + \frac{C_e}{Q_{m,1}} \quad (4)$$

Freundlich isotherm model Equation 5:

$$\ln Q_e = \ln k_f + \frac{1}{n} \ln C_e \quad (5)$$

where C_e (mg L^{-1}) is the equilibrium concentration of HA, b (L mg^{-1}) and $Q_{m,1}$ (mg g^{-1}) are the Langmuir constant and the monolayer adsorption capacity, respectively; n and K_F [$(\text{L mg}^{-1})^{1/n} \text{mg/g}$] are related to adsorption intensity and capacity.

Results and Discussion

Characterization

Crystal Structure by XRD

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns displayed peak shifts with changes in anion composition, indicating alterations in the molecular structure of the synthesized MOFs from figure 2. These patterns closely align with their simulated XRD profile of single-crystalline, confirming the structural integrity and similarity of the synthesized MOF samples to the well-established crystalline framework of bulk.

The sharp peaks of UiO-66(Zr) indicate a high degree of crystallinity, which is expected for UiO-66(Zr) as known for its stable Zr-based MOF structure. Peaks at $2\theta = 7.5$ and 8° values that closely match the simulated pattern confirm

the successful synthesis of the UiO-66(Zr) framework, with characteristic pore sizes and metal-ligand coordination geometry. Notably, on UiO-66(Zr) XRD graph a shift observed in the peak at $2\theta = 7.5$ and 8° towards lower angles suggesting a resultant expansion in the lattice spacing. This shift underscores the influence of nitrate ions on the structural parameters of the UiO-66(Zr), highlighting its adaptable nature and the potential for tailored porosity through chemical modification.

MIL-100(Fe) also shows sharp, well-defined peaks, indicating a pure phase and high crystallinity. The alignment with the simulated pattern suggests that the Fe centers are correctly coordinated with the organic linkers, forming the characteristic large pores of MIL-100. Notably, a discernible shift in the peak within the 2θ range of $10\text{--}12^\circ$ towards lower angles was observed as the concentration of NO^3 ions increased. This shift is indicative of an expansion in the lattice spacing, suggesting that the inclusion of NO^3 ions directly influences the structural parameters of MIL-100(Fe), potentially allowing for controlled modification of its porosity and interstitial characteristics.

Textural Properties by N_2 Sorption

The characteristics and performance of the of MOFs are assessed in detail for nitrogen (N_2) adsorption capabilities from Figure 4.2. The Table 4.1 includes data from Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET), Langmuir surface area and total pore volume measurements which offer insights into the surface area and porosity of the MOFs.

UiO-66(Zr) exhibits a high surface area with a BET surface area of $1378 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and a Langmuir surface area of $1514 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, which indicates its potential for gas adsorption and catalysis applications. The difference between BET and Langmuir surface areas suggests heterogeneity in pore sizes or shapes. UiO-66(Zr) exhibits a moderate pore volume with total pore volume of $0.56 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$, which supports its decent adsorption capacity for smaller molecules. Although it doesn't have the highest pore

volume, its structural stability due to zirconium centers allows it to maintain its integrity in harsh conditions, thus maintaining consistent adsorption performance under thermal and chemical stresses. The pore size or pore aperture is around $6\text{--}7 \text{ \AA}$, which is the size of the benzene ring (Winarta et al., 2020). The N_2 isotherm graph of UiO-66(Zr) shows a steady increase in the quantity adsorbed as relative pressure increases, with a slight curvature before reaching a plateau. The curve suggests a Type I isotherm which characteristics for microporous materials. The adsorption curve rapidly increases at low relative pressures, indicating the presence of micropores where nitrogen molecules are quickly adsorbed. The desorption curve follows a similar path to the adsorption curve, showing little hysteresis, which suggests that the pores are accessible and there are no significant issues with pore blocking or network effects.

MIL-100(Fe) exhibits a high BET surface area of $1600 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, with a Langmuir surface area of $2013 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. This denotes an extremely high porosity and potential for applications requiring maximum surface contact, such as catalysis or high-capacity gas storage. Similarly, to UiO-66(Zr), MIL-100 Fe has total pore volume of $0.56 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$, which possesses a pore volume that supports moderate adsorption capacity. However, its iron-based composition and larger pore size make it especially suited for the adsorption of larger molecules than UiO-66(Zr), such as benzene and other aromatic compounds. MIL-100(Fe) is an iron(III) carboxylate material with larger pore sizes of around $25\text{--}27 \text{ \AA}$, which is approximately the size of a benzene molecule (Chen, Zhou, Xu, Ding, & Cheng, 2019).

The N_2 isotherm curve for of MIL-100(Fe) indicates type IV isotherm with a hysteresis loop, typically associated with mesoporous materials. The adsorption curve exhibits a steep increase at moderate relative pressures, indicating mesoporous structures. The desorption curve forms a hysteresis loop, which is typical for materials with mesopores and capillary condensation. This indicates that the pores are larger than those in UiO-66(Zr).

Figure 3. PXRD Patterns for a) UiO-66 (Zr), b) MIL-100 Fe Pristine State

Figure 4. N₂ Adsorption/Desorption Isotherms of a) UiO-66(Zr), b) MIL-100(Fe) Pristine State

Table 2. Porous Properties for the Synthesized MOFs

MOF	Surface area m ² /g		Total pore volume cm ³ /g
	BET	Langmuir	
UiO-66(Zr)	1378	1514	0.56
MIL-100(Fe)	1600	2013	0.56

Morphology by SEM

Morphology of UiO-66(Zr) typically exhibits a highly regular, octahedral morphology, which is consistent across the range of images provided from image (a,b) in Figure 4.3. The octahedral

shape is a direct consequence of the Zr₆O₄(OH)₄ clusters and the way the organic linkers (1,4-benzenedicarboxylate, BDC) bridge these clusters, contributing to the overall cubic structure of the framework.

Image (a) at lower magnifications, we see a high density of particles with a relatively uniform size and shape. The particles appear to be tightly packed, suggesting that the sample has a high surface area, which is a desirable characteristic for MOFs used in gas storage or catalysis. The image (b) provides close-ups of individual crystals, where we can appreciate the geometric regularity and the sharpness of the edges. The surfaces appear smooth, with no visible defects or impurities, which suggests high purity and crystallinity of the synthesized material.

The SEM images of UiO-66(Zr) particles highlight their uniform size and distinct octahedral shape, indicative of high-quality crystals. This shape consistency suggests a controlled synthesis process and minimal impurities. The relationship between the composite and ligands is crucial, with $Zr_6O_4(OH)_4$ clusters serving as nodes and BDC ligands as linkers. This arrangement results in a highly porous structure with robust Zr-O bonds, ensuring chemical and thermal stability. Overall, these characteristics reflect an optimized synthesis protocol, promising excellent performance in practical applications.

SEM images of MIL-100(Fe) displays a polyhedral morphology with relatively uniform size distribution as shown from image (c,d) of Figure 4.3. The magnification allows us to estimate the size of the particles, which appear to be in the micrometer range. The smooth faces and edges suggest a high degree of crystallinity, which is characteristic of well-formed MOFs.

From image (c) we can observe the distinct shape of the crystals more clearly. They seem to maintain the same polyhedral shape with smoother surfaces, indicating a consistent growth pattern and suggesting a controlled synthesis process. The image (d) appears to show a cluster of crystals. Some of the crystals exhibit well-defined shapes, while others are less distinct, possibly due to aggregation or incomplete crystallization.

In summary, the SEM images suggest that MIL-100(Fe) has been synthesized with a degree of uniformity in shape and size, indicating a well-controlled synthesis process. The presence of

striations and layers on the crystal surface may suggest differing growth rates on different facets, possibly influenced by ligands during synthesis.

Chemical Structure by FTIR

UiO-66(Zr) peak shifts were observed in FTIR spectra from Figure 4.4, providing further confirmation of structural synthesized UiO-66(Zr) MOF. Observed Peaks at 3673.8 cm^{-1} suggests O-H stretching vibrations, indicative of moisture or hydroxyl groups within the framework. Band at 1506.5 cm^{-1} : Attributed to the aromatic C=C stretching vibrations from the organic linker, typically terephthalic acid in UiO-66(Zr). Peak of 739.3 cm^{-1} as characteristic of Zr-O stretching, confirming the metal-organic framework's composition and structure. Broad band near 3400 cm^{-1} points to O-H stretching from water or hydroxyl units. Peak around 1587 cm^{-1} Likely represents the C=O stretching vibration, consistent with the terephthalate ligands in UiO-66(Zr). For characteristic peaks, the fingerprint region (below 1000 cm^{-1}) showcases the Zr-O bonds, critical for the UiO-66(Zr) framework.

MIL-100(Fe) peak shifts were observed in FTIR spectra from Figure 4.4, providing further confirmation of structural synthesized MIL-100 Fe MOF. Peaks at 3674 cm^{-1} and 3610 cm^{-1} are slightly visible, could be attributed to O-H stretching, but less pronounced due to the material's structure. Distinct Peak at 1384.6 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of carboxylate groups, indicating the organic linker's interaction with iron. The presence of peaks around 750 cm^{-1} and below points towards Fe-O vibrations, aligning with the expected structure of MIL-100 Fe. Broad peak around 3400 cm^{-1} Similar to Al-fum, indicating hydroxyl groups or water content. Distinct peaks around 1600 cm^{-1} and 1384 cm^{-1} can be attributed to asymmetric and symmetric stretching of carboxylate groups (COO-), resonating with the trimesate ligands commonly associated with MIL-100 Fe. Peaks near $800\text{-}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest the presence of Fe-O bonds, which are crucial for the structural integrity of the MOF. FTIR spectra showed an obvious peak shift from 711 cm^{-1} and 1385 cm^{-1} in MIL-

100(Fe), confirming the existence of Fe (II) in the samples, by suggesting a change in the bond strength or the coordination environment of the Fe (II) ions in the samples. when there is a

change in the oxidation state of the metal ions, such as the reduction of Fe (III) to Fe (II) in this case.

Figure 5. FT-IR Spectra of a) UiO-66(Zr), b) MIL-100(Fe), c) HA, d) Kaolin

Removal of Humic Acid by MOF Adsorption

Kinetic Adsorption

The result of the effect of contact time on the adsorption of humic acid (HA) over UiO-66(Zr) is presented in Figure 4.5. In graph (a) the adsorption of UiO-66(Zr) over time demonstrates a gradual decrease in adsorption

rate, indicating a transition from rapid adsorption to equilibrium. This suggests a high affinity of UiO-66(Zr) for adsorbate molecules.

The pseudo-second-order kinetic model exhibits an excellent fit to the experimental data, as evidenced by the high Pearson correlation coefficient (0.99978) and R-square value (0.99956), indicating that nearly all of the

variability in the adsorption data can be explained by the model. The very low residual sum of squares further corroborates the model's accuracy in describing the adsorption process. A better fit with the pseudo-second-order model suggests that the rate-limiting step might be chemical adsorption (chemisorption) involving valence forces through sharing or exchange of electrons between UiO-66(Zr) and the adsorbate.

The results of the kinetic data analysis are summarized in Table 4.2, where the regression

coefficients (R^2) and residual sum of squares (RSS) were compared to determine the best-fit model. It was found that there was no good linear relationship between the pseudo-first-order model and the experimental data. However, the pseudo-second-order kinetic model exhibits an excellent fit to the experimental data, as evidenced by the high Pearson correlation coefficient (0.99844) and R-square value (0.99608), indicating that the adsorption is primarily controlled by chemical adsorption

Figure 6. SEM Images of (a,b) UiO-66(Zr), (c,d) MIL-100(Fe) in Pristine State

Table 3. Fitting Parameters of Pseudo-First-Order, Pseudo-Second-Order Model

Adsorbent	C_0 (mg/g)	$q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)	Pseudo-first-order model			Pseudo-second-order model		
			$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	K_1 (1/min)	R^2	$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	K_2 g/(mg·min)	R^2
UiO-66(Zr)	50	26.52	27.87	-0.0006	0.915	28.43	0.011	0.99989
MIL-100(Fe)	50	29.5	10.1	-0.0002	0.167	36.15	0.0024	0.996

Figure 7. Effect of Contact Time on Adsorption onto a) UiO-66(Zr), b) MIL-100(Fe) MOF (pH = 6, Adsorbent Dosage = 40 mg, Volume = 0.08 L, Initial Concentration = 50 mg/L, Temperature = 305 K) with Pseudo-First-Order Plot and Pseudo-Second-Order Experiments

Effect of Initial pH

The result of initial effect of pH varied on adsorption capacity of UiO-66(Zr) observed from Figure 4.6, at acidic pH (4-6) initial observation, contrary to typical expectations, Q_t is higher in acidic conditions for UiO-66(Zr), this indicates a favorable interaction between HA and the MOF under these conditions. The acidic environment protonates HA, but instead of reducing its interaction with UiO-66(Zr), this facilitates specific interactions with the zirconium nodes or the terephthalate ligands. The presence of excess H^+ ions could potentially lead to a scenario where HA is more compact or its conformation is altered, promoting its interaction with the MOF. Additionally, the slight protonation of the terephthalate ligands could enhance their ability to interact with HA through hydrogen bonding or other mechanisms.

MIL-100 Fe features iron trimer clusters connected by tricarboxylate ligands, which may exhibit different behaviors under varying pH due to the metal centers' propensity to undergo hydrolysis. The increased Q_t at pH 4 suggests that MIL-100 Fe is more effective in adsorbing the targeted adsorbate under acidic conditions. This could be due to several factors, including the protonation of carboxylate ligands and the enhanced electrostatic attraction between the MOF and negatively charged adsorbate molecules.

Effect of Adsorbent Dosage on Isotherm Adsorption

Nonlinear regression of the experimental data yielded the isotherm results shown in Table 4.3. The parameter K_f varies for each MOFs, revealing the endothermic nature of adsorption. The model expression for both studies of kinetic and isotherm adsorption studies have been given

from Table 4.4.

Adsorption isotherm of UiO-66(Zr) has been provided from Figure 4.7 (a). The Langmuir model presupposes uniform adsorption sites for monolayer coverage. The q value signifies the high adsorption capacity of UiO-66(Zr), albeit lower than some other MOFs, while k suggests a strong interaction between the adsorbate and UiO-66(Zr). The R-Square value of 0.928 indicates better fit.

Adsorption isotherm for MIL-100(Fe) has been provided from Figure 4.7 (b), the Langmuir

equation is defined by $q=129.45 \text{ mg/g}$ (maximum adsorption capacity) and $k=0.128$ (adsorption affinity constant). This indicates a relatively good fit, suggesting that MIL-100(Fe) might have more uniform adsorption sites than UiO-66(Zr), which could be due to its iron-based clusters and larger pores. The Langmuir isotherm assumes monolayer adsorption on a homogeneous surface with finite identical sites. The relatively higher R-Square value (0.95) suggests a better fit than Freundlich model, indicating that the real adsorption behavior follow the ideal monolayer assumption.

Figure 8. Initial pH Effect on Adsorption Capacity of a) UiO-66(Zr), b) MIL-100(Fe), c) ZIF-8, d) Al-fum MOFs (Adsorbent Dosage = 40 mg, Volume = 0.08 L, Initial Concentration = 50 mg/L, Temperature = 305 K, Contact Time= Equilibrium Time of each MOFs

Table 4. Fitting Parameters of Langmuir and Freundlich Isotherm Models

Adsorbent	Temperature (K)	Langmuir			Freundlich		
		$q_{\max}$ (mg/g)	K_L	R^2	K_F	n	R^2
UiO-66(Zr)	305	60.14	0.387	0.928	14.7	3.36	0.87
MIL-100(Fe)	305	129.45	0.128	0.95	20	2.53	0.855

Figure 8. Adsorption Isotherm of a) UiO-66(Zr), b) MIL-100(Fe) (pH= best pH Removal of its each MOFs, dosage= 40 mg, Volume Solution= 80 mL, Temperature= 305 K, Initial HA Concentration= 50 mg/L, Contact Time= Equilibrium Time of Its Each MOF)

Table 4. Model Expressions for Kinetics and Isotherm Studies

Model/Function name	Expression	Parameters/Description
Kinetic		
Pseudo first order model	$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln (q_e) - k_1 t$	q_e (mg/g), equilibrium adsorption uptake
		q_t (mg/g), instantaneous adsorption uptake
		k_1 (1/min), pseudo first order rate constant
Pseudo second order model	$t/q_t = 1/K_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e t$	k_2 (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹), pseudo second order rate constant
Isotherm		
Two-parameter model		
Freundlich	$q = K_F C_e^{1/n_F}$	C_e (mg/L), equilibrium concentration
		K_F [(mg/g) (L mg ⁻¹) ^{1/n}], adsorption uptake constant
		n_F , Freundlich parameter
Langmuir	$q = q_{max} K_L C / (1 + K_L C)$	q_{max} (mg/g) maximum adsorption capacity of the adsorbent
		C_e (mg/L), equilibrium concentration
		K_L (L/mg) is the Langmuir constant

Characterization of MOFs after Adsorption

Crystal Structure by XRD

XRD patterns for after adsorption dry MOF samples show that These observations imply that the ligands and metal nodes in these MOFs are able to withstand the adsorption process without significant degradation or structural

collapse.

XRD pattern of UiO-66(Zr) after adsorption remains relatively unchanged as shown from Figure 4.8, suggesting that the adsorption process does not significantly alter the crystalline structure of UiO-66(Zr). The preservation of peak positions and intensities implies that the framework remains intact and that adsorption

occurs without disrupting the structural integrity. These interactions, however, do not seem to alter the overall framework, suggesting that adsorption occurs mainly within the pores without affecting the MOF's backbone.

UiO-66(Zr)'s resilience to structural changes upon adsorption is likely due to its robust zirconium-based nodes and strong ligand connections. This stability is crucial for applications requiring repeated adsorption-desorption cycles. The inherent stability of UiO-66(Zr) can be attributed to the strong Zr-O bonds and the protective effect of the organic ligands. The rigidity of the framework, combined with the spatial arrangement of its components, contributes to its resilience against structural deformations during adsorption.

The XRD pattern of MIL-100(Fe) after adsorption shows slight alterations in peak intensities from Figure 4.8 (b), suggesting minor changes in the crystal lattice, possibly due to the interaction between the adsorbate and the iron centers or ligands. However, the overall crystallinity appears to be preserved.

The preservation of the crystalline structure of MIL-100(Fe) after adsorption indicates the robustness of its framework. This suggests that adsorption does not significantly alter the MOF's overall structure, aligning with the expectation of MIL-100(Fe)'s stability under adsorptive stress. The slight changes in peak intensity could hint at interactions between the adsorbed molecules and the framework, possibly affecting the electron density or causing minor rearrangements within the pores. The iron (III) clusters and organic ligands in MIL-100(Fe) confer a high degree of chemical stability to the framework, enabling it to withstand the introduction of adsorbate molecules without significant structural alterations. Some MOFs, including MIL-100(Fe), exhibit a degree of flexibility, allowing them to accommodate adsorbate molecules through minor structural adjustments that do not compromise the overall crystallinity.

Chemical Structure by FTIR

For UiO-66(Zr) after adsorption, peaks of

1583.8 cm^{-1} & 1507.7 cm^{-1} representing the carboxylate groups appear slightly shifted or altered in intensity as shown from Figure 4.9 (a), suggesting interactions between the adsorbate molecules and the carboxylate functionalities, which may affect their electronic environment. 1392 cm^{-1} peak, slightly shifted from the pre-adsorption spectrum, could indicate a change in the aromatic ring structures, possibly due to π - π interactions with the adsorbate. 1020.8 cm^{-1} shows a notable shift from 1067.6 cm^{-1} , which might reflect changes in C-O stretching vibrations, suggesting that adsorption affects ether or ester groups within the framework. 731.7 cm^{-1} , 677 cm^{-1} , 561.3 cm^{-1} , and 473 cm^{-1} the presence of these peaks post-adsorption, with slight shifts or changes in intensity, suggests that the framework's overall integrity is retained, with possible minor adjustments in the inorganic-organic interactions within the MOF structure.

Changes in peaks related to carboxylate groups and aromatic rings suggest significant interactions between adsorbate molecules and these functional groups, possibly via hydrogen bonding or π - π interactions. These interactions influence the MOF's adsorption behavior, electronic properties, and structure. Shifts in C-O stretching vibrations post-adsorption indicate potential alterations in ether or ester functionalities, impacting the framework's flexibility or porosity. Despite these changes, the MOF's overall structure seems preserved, evident from consistent metal-organic bending and stretching vibrations in pre- and post-adsorption spectra.

For MIL-100(Fe) after adsorption, no O-H stretching peak around 3674 cm^{-1} as shown from Figure 4.9 (b). This absence post-adsorption suggests that water molecules or hydroxyl groups have interacted or been displaced by the adsorbate. The C-H stretching peaks at 2991 cm^{-1} and 2900 cm^{-1} remain relatively unchanged, this indicates the stability of the organic components of the framework during adsorption. The shift in the C=O stretching vibration from 1634.5 cm^{-1} to 1632.5 cm^{-1} suggests interaction between the adsorbate and the carboxylate groups, potentially altering their electronic environment. The C-H bending and carboxylate stretching

vibrations 1450 cm^{-1} , 1382.9 cm^{-1} reflects changes in the organic ligands' environment due to adsorption. C-O stretching vibrations around 1067.6 cm^{-1} indicate interactions involving ether or ester functionalities within the MOF structure. Metal-oxygen vibrations (710.9 cm^{-1} and 631.7 cm^{-1}) suggests that the inorganic framework's integrity is largely retained, with minor adjustments possibly reflecting a tighter integration of the adsorbate within the MOF structure.

The stability of C-H stretching vibrations post-adsorption highlights the resilience of organic components within the framework. Conversely, shifts in C=O stretching and C-H bending vibrations suggest interactions with adsorbate molecules, potentially altering the electronic environment of carboxylate groups. These interactions can impact the MOF's adsorption properties, influencing selectivity and capacity for different adsorbates. While maintaining overall structural integrity, observed slight alterations in spectra indicate molecular-level changes that may enhance or diminish the framework's effectiveness for specific

applications.

Morphology by SEM

The individual octahedral crystals of UiO-66(Zr) are more prominently visible from Figure 4.10 (a). We can see the rougher texture of each crystal surface, suggesting possible adsorption sites or surface modifications, meanwhile in pristine state tends to exhibit cleaner. The shape of UiO-66 MOFs is typically octahedral or cubic for both states.

MIL-100(Fe) in after adsorption state maintains its polyhedral crystal shape with no significant morphological changes as shown from Figure 4.10 (b). The uniformity of the crystal size and the preservation of the surface morphology post-adsorption suggest that the adsorption process does not adversely affect the structural integrity of the MOF. Minor surface roughness and occasional agglomerations could be indicative of interactions with adsorbed molecules, but overall, the MIL-100(Fe) seems to show excellent stability and retention of its crystalline structure after adsorption, across the different magnifications observed.

Figure 9. PXRD Curves for a) UiO-66 (Zr), b) MIL-100 Fe of Synthesized and after Adsorption MOFs

Figure 10. FT-IR Spectra of a) UiO-66 (Zr), b) MIL-100 Fe after Adsorption

Figure 11. SEM Images of a) UiO-66(Zr), b) MIL-100(Fe) after Adsorption

Conclusions

This study undertakes a profound exploration of the potential of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) in water purification, particularly targeting the removal of humic acid (HA) from aquatic systems. We synthesized and applied two distinct MOFs- UiO-66 (Zr), MIL-100 (Fe) and assessed the optimal adsorption capacity, preferred pH for HA removal, and the equilibrium time for each MOFs.

- UiO-66 (Zr), with its rapid equilibrium

time of under 15 minutes and an adsorption capacity of 60 mg/g, and basic environment enhance the performance best.

- MIL-100 (Fe) achieved rapid equilibrium time and a (129mg/g) adsorption capacity which is higher than UiO-66(Zr), and similarly to UiO-66(Zr) basic condition helps better in HA removing.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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